

Supplementary Tables and Figures for :

**Dairy herd response to annual heat load mainly differ depending on geographical localization, calving distribution and milk yield.
A study based on commercial data-farm.**

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Summary of the study

This study investigated the herd-level effects of annual heat load in 3,393 French commercial dairy herds monitored over 12 to 24 years between 2000 and 2023. Annual heat exposure was quantified using a Cumulative Annual Temperature–Humidity Index (CATHI), developed to characterize the yearly heat load experienced at each herd location. Using herd-year performance data, the study showed that annual heat load negatively affected several key herd performance indicators, including milk yield, lactation duration, number of recalving cows, productive longevity, and herd size. Herds located in areas less frequently exposed to heat stress showed greater performance losses than herds from more exposed areas, suggesting possible climatic acclimatization or adaptation. Calving distribution also modulated herd responses: herds with year-round calving showed lower losses than herds with grouped winter or fall calving. Higher-producing herds were more strongly affected by annual heat load, whereas breed composition, primiparous rate, and herd size had limited influence. Overall, this study showed that dairy herd responses to heat load depend on herd-level organization and climatic context, highlighting the potential role of structural adaptation and management flexibility, especially calving distribution, in herd resilience to climate change.

Table S1. Number of herd studied per year over the period 2000 to 2023.

Years	Number of herds included in th study
2000	1145
2001	1164
2002	1442
2003	1702
2004	1775
2005	1826
2006	1864
2007	1904
2008	2043
2009	2470
2010	3120
2011	3356
2012	3393
2013	3387
2014	3381
2015	3375
2016	3367
2017	3363
2018	3358
2019	3348
2020	3327
2021	3296
2022	3266
2023	3152

Table S2. Comparison of climatic variables between areas : Mean \pm SD of meteorological data at herds locations in overall studied area (ALL) and in Auvergne (AUV), Littoral Atlantique (LI-A), Littoral Normand (LI-N) and Nord-Est Loire (NE-L).

AREA	Annual climatic variables calculated at herd location*			
	mean_ T_{max} °C	mean_ T_{av} °C	mean_ P_{sum} mm	mean_ T_{range} °C
ALL	25.4 \pm 1.4	11.1 \pm 1.3	907 \pm 142	28.8 \pm 2.3
AUV	24.9 \pm 1.5 ^b	9.3 \pm 1.3 ^a	1005 \pm 194 ^d	31.8 \pm 0.5 ^d
LI-A	26.7 \pm 0.6 ^d	12.4 \pm 0.3 ^d	836 \pm 34 ^b	28.7 \pm 0.8 ^b
LI-N	24.4 \pm 1.0 ^a	11.1 \pm 0.4 ^b	952 \pm 93 ^c	26.7 \pm 2.0 ^a
NE-L	26.4 \pm 0.7 ^c	11.7 \pm 0.4 ^c	788 \pm 63 ^a	29.2 \pm 0.7 ^c

^{a-d}Means within a column with different superscripts differ ($P < 0.05$), Dunn post-hoc test.

mean_ T_{max} : average maximal temperature in °C

mean_ T_{av} : annual average temperatures in °C

mean_ P_{sum} : annual sum of precipitation in mm

mean_ T_{range} : annual temperature range in °C

*For the climatic area description, daily measures from the SAFRAN time series were used for each mesh of the grid corresponding to the herd location (average daily temperature, °C, and daily precipitation, mm; 1,206 SAFRAN meshes). From daily weather series at each herd location, we derived four annual indicators: mean daily temperature (T_{av}), annual maximum daily temperature (T_{max}), annual temperature range (T_{range} ; annual max–min temperature), and annual precipitation sum (P_{sum}). For each area, long-term climatic conditions were summarized as the 2000–2023 mean of these annual indicators (mean_ T_{av} , mean_ T_{max} , mean_ T_{range} , mean_ P_{sum}).

Overall, Auvergne (AUV) was the coolest area (mean_ T_{av} = 9.3°C) with a large thermal amplitude (mean_ T_{range} = 31.8°C) and high but spatially variable precipitation (mean_ P_{sum} = 1,005 \pm 142 mm). Littoral Atlantique (LI-A) was the warmest (mean_ T_{av} = 12.4°C) and showed the highest mean_ T_{max} (26.7°C). Littoral Normand (LI-N) had the lowest mean_ T_{max} (24.4°C) and the smallest thermal amplitude (mean_ T_{range} = 26.7°C), with relatively high rainfall (mean_ P_{sum} = 952 \pm 93 mm). The Nord-Est Loire (NE-L) combined high temperatures (mean_ T_{av} = 11.7°C; mean_ T_{max} = 26.4°C) with the lowest precipitation (mean_ P_{sum} = 788 \pm 63 mm).

Table S3 - Variables considered to study the effects of annual heat load on herd performance, and associated explanatory variables, measured at herd-year (HY) level and scaled in the models.

Variable type	Variable	Name	Description
explained (Res _{Y_{ij}})	Herd performances residuals to measure resilience <i>HY level</i>	Res_MY305: annual deviation of Milk yield	Annual residuals from trend of the 305 days average milk yield corrected by the rate of primiparous cows in the herd (kg/cow)
		Res_Fat305: annual deviation of fat content	Annual residuals from trend of the 305-d average milk fat content (g/kg/cow)
		Res_Prot305: annual deviation of protein content	Annual residuals from trend of the 305-d average milk protein content (g/kg/cow)
		Res_Duration: annual deviation of lactation duration	Annual residuals from trend of the average duration of lactation (d/cow)
		Res_CalvInt: annual deviation of calving interval	Annual residuals from trend of the average duration of the calving interval (d/cow)
		Res_Calv: annual deviation of recalvings number	Annual residuals from trend of the log number of cows that recalve the following year, corrected by herd size (log(cow))
		Res_Long: annual deviation of cows longevity	Annual residuals from trend of the average productive longevity of cows in the herd, from first calving day to end of the last lactation (d/cow)
		Res_Size: annual deviation of herd size	Annual residuals from trend of the log number of cows in lactation in the herd (log(cow))
explanatory (CATHI _{ij})	Hazards quantification <i>HY level</i>	CATHI: Cumulative Annual Temperature Humidity Index	Annual sum of daily THI units above the threshold of 68.8 (dimensionless)
explanatory (X _{herd,ij})	Variables influencing herd resilience <i>HY level</i> variables except for Area (unchanged for the time series)	Area: Geographical area	Code AUV LI-A LI-N NE-L
		Breed _{herd} : Main breed	Code HO MX MB NM OB
		Season _{herd} : Main calving season	Code FA WI SP SU NO_S
		MY305 _{herd} : Mean annual milk per cow	kg/cow
		Size _{herd} : Annual number of cows	Number of cows in lactation
		Prim _{herd} : Annual primiparous rate	Percentage of cows in their first lactation
<i>random (H)</i>	Identification	<i>Herd: Herd identity</i>	<i>Unique identifier of each herd</i>

Area: LI-N = Littoral Normand, NE-L = Nord-Est Loire; LI-A = Littoral Atlantique; AUV = Auvergne ; Breed_{herd}: HO = Holstein; MB = Montbéliarde; NM = Normande; OB = Other Breeds; MX = Mixed with <60% of main breed. Season_{herd}: SP = spring (April, May, June); SU = summer (July, August, September); FA = fall (October, November, December); WI = winter (January, February, March); NO_S with <40% of calving on each season.

Table S4. Standardized estimates (mean) of regression coefficients β_1 , β_2 and β_3 , their standard errors (se) and associated p-values from each of 8 mixed model explaining herd responses from annual trend-deviation of performances (Res_Yij: Res_MY305, Res_Fat305, Res_Prot305, Res_Duration, Res_CalvInt, Res_Calv, Res_Long and Res_Size) as a function of CATHIj of current year* or CATHIj-1 of previous year, depending on 6 herd characteristics (Milk305herd, Prim herd, Size herd, Breedherd, Season herd, Area), with herd as random effect [Res_Yij = $\beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot \text{CATHIj} + \beta_2 \cdot \text{Xherd}_{kij} + \beta_3 \cdot \text{CATHIj} \cdot \text{Xherd}_{kij} + (1 | \text{Herdi}) + \epsilon_{ij}$]. All variables were scaled for modelling with multivariate linear mixed-model.**

Mixed Model coefficients for fixed effects	Res_MY305*			Res_Fat305*			Res_Prot305*			Res_Duration*			Res_CalvInt*			Res_Calv*			Res_Long**			Res_Size**		
	mean	Se	p-value	mean	Se	p-value	mean	se	p-value	mean	se	p-value	mean	se	p-value	mean	se	p-value	mean	se	p-value	mean	se	p-value
Intercept (β_0)	0.58	0.03	0.00	-0.06	0.04	0.08	0.10	0.04	0.01	-0.18	0.03	0.00	-0.03	0.04	0.36	-0.08	0.04	0.03	0.06	0.04	0.09	-0.23	0.05	0.00
CATHI (β_1)	-0.11	0.03	0.00	0.05	0.01	0.00	-0.01	0.01	0.19	-0.10	0.03	0.00	-0.03	0.01	0.00	-0.14	0.01	0.00	-0.18	0.04	0.00	-0.23	0.01	0.00
MY305 _{herd} (β_2)	0.57	0.00	0.00	-0.10	0.01	0.00	0.05	0.01	0.00	0.20	0.00	0.00	0.11	0.01	0.00	0.03	0.01	0.00	0.11	0.01	0.00	-0.27	0.01	0.00
Prim _{herd} (β_2)	-0.27	0.00	0.00	-0.01	0.00	0.01	-0.02	0.00	0.00	-0.51	0.00	0.00	-0.27	0.00	0.00	0.07	0.00	0.00	-0.20	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.00
Size _{herd} (β_2)	-0.06	0.00	0.00	-0.02	0.00	0.00	-0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.10	-0.01	0.00	0.00	-0.08	0.00	0.00	-0.03	0.00	0.00	0.97	0.01	0.00
Area=LI-A (β_2)	-0.21	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.35	-0.08	0.02	0.00	0.10	0.01	0.00	0.13	0.02	0.00	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.06	0.02	0.00	-0.22	0.04	0.00
Area=LI-N (β_2)	-0.38	0.01	0.00	0.25	0.02	0.00	0.10	0.02	0.00	-0.06	0.01	0.00	-0.09	0.02	0.00	-0.18	0.02	0.00	-0.25	0.02	0.00	-0.56	0.04	0.00
Area=NE-L (β_2)	-0.33	0.01	0.00	0.10	0.02	0.00	-0.06	0.02	0.00	0.09	0.01	0.00	0.08	0.02	0.00	-0.08	0.02	0.00	0.02	0.02	0.20	-0.04	0.04	0.31
Breed _{herd} =MX (β_2)	-0.15	0.03	0.00	-0.06	0.04	0.11	-0.12	0.04	0.00	0.06	0.03	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.27	-0.07	0.04	0.06	-0.02	0.04	0.67	0.34	0.04	0.00
Breed _{herd} =MB (β_2)	-0.30	0.03	0.00	-0.06	0.04	0.08	-0.15	0.04	0.00	-0.12	0.03	0.00	-0.07	0.04	0.06	-0.05	0.04	0.21	-0.07	0.04	0.05	0.25	0.05	0.00
Breed _{herd} =NM (β_2)	0.08	0.03	0.02	-0.09	0.04	0.01	-0.07	0.04	0.05	0.18	0.03	0.00	0.08	0.04	0.02	-0.08	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.38	0.41	0.05	0.00
Breed _{herd} =HO (β_2)	-0.60	0.03	0.00	-0.01	0.04	0.83	-0.20	0.04	0.00	-0.02	0.03	0.51	0.00	0.04	0.89	-0.10	0.03	0.01	-0.05	0.04	0.14	0.45	0.04	0.00
Season _{herd} =NO_S (β_2)	0.06	0.01	0.00	-0.01	0.01	0.49	0.07	0.01	0.00	0.18	0.01	0.00	-0.01	0.01	0.36	0.31	0.01	0.00	-0.01	0.01	0.36	0.12	0.01	0.00
Season _{herd} =SP (β_2)	0.04	0.02	0.08	0.01	0.02	0.58	0.10	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.78	0.02	0.03	0.48	0.01	0.02	0.80	-0.01	0.03	0.62	-0.16	0.02	0.00
Season _{herd} =SU (β_2)	0.01	0.01	0.21	0.12	0.01	0.00	0.22	0.01	0.00	0.15	0.01	0.00	-0.06	0.01	0.00	0.19	0.01	0.00	-0.04	0.01	0.00	0.29	0.01	0.00
Season _{herd} =WI (β_2)	0.11	0.02	0.00	-0.06	0.02	0.01	-0.02	0.02	0.46	-0.19	0.02	0.00	-0.04	0.03	0.09	-0.12	0.02	0.00	-0.03	0.03	0.33	-0.20	0.02	0.00
MY305 _{herd} ·CATHI (β_3)	-0.05	0.00	0.00	0.05	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.00	-0.04	0.00	0.00	-0.01	0.00	0.00	-0.02	0.00	0.00	-0.05	0.01	0.00	-	-	-
Prim _{herd} ·CATHI (β_3)	-0.02	0.00	0.00	-0.01	0.00	0.00	-	-	-	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.00
Size _{herd} ·CATHI (β_3)	-0.01	0.00	0.07	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	-0.01	0.00	0.01	-0.03	0.00	0.00	-0.05	0.00	0.00	-0.02	0.00	0.00	-0.12	0.00	0.00
Area=LI-A·CATHI (β_3)	0.01	0.01	0.26	0.05	0.01	0.00	0.06	0.01	0.00	-0.06	0.01	0.00	-0.07	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.39	-0.04	0.01	0.00	-0.07	0.01	0.00
Area=LI-N·CATHI (β_3)	-0.20	0.02	0.00	0.30	0.02	0.00	0.26	0.02	0.00	-0.23	0.02	0.00	-0.27	0.02	0.00	-0.23	0.02	0.00	-0.42	0.02	0.00	-0.11	0.01	0.00
Area=NE-L·CATHI (β_3)	0.07	0.01	0.00	-0.06	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	1.00	-0.01	0.01	0.31	0.03	0.01	0.02	0.09	0.01	0.00	0.07	0.01	0.00	-0.15	0.01	0.00
Breed _{herd} =MX·CATHI (β_3)	-0.03	0.03	0.38	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.03	0.03	0.41	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.07	0.04	0.09	-	-	-
Breed _{herd} =MB·CATHI (β_3)	0.02	0.03	0.62	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.09	0.03	0.01	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.06	0.04	0.12	-	-	-
Breed _{herd} =NM·CATHI (β_3)	-0.01	0.03	0.87	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.08	0.03	0.02	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.10	0.04	0.02	-	-	-
Breed _{herd} =HO·CATHI (β_3)	-0.02	0.03	0.46	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.07	0.03	0.03	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.15	0.04	0.00	-	-	-
Season _{herd} =NO_S·CATHI (β_3)	0.04	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.76	0.03	0.01	0.00	0.07	0.01	0.00	-	-	-	0.09	0.01	0.00	-0.06	0.01	0.00	0.12	0.01	0.00
Season _{herd} =SP·CATHI (β_3)	0.03	0.02	0.23	0.06	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.26	-0.13	0.02	0.00	-	-	-	-0.10	0.03	0.00	-0.07	0.03	0.03	-0.16	0.02	0.00
Season _{herd} =SU·CATHI (β_3)	0.04	0.01	0.00	-0.01	0.01	0.44	0.04	0.01	0.00	0.08	0.01	0.00	-	-	-	0.06	0.01	0.00	-0.01	0.01	0.65	0.20	0.01	0.00
Season _{herd} =WI·CATHI (β_3)	-0.05	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.02	0.89	-0.01	0.02	0.58	-0.16	0.02	0.00	-	-	-	-0.16	0.02	0.00	-0.06	0.03	0.08	-0.16	0.02	0.00

- concerns non-retained variables by the selection procedure ; in bold significant coefficient (p-value<0.05 for Student test)

Res_MY305 = Annual trend-deviation of average milk yield at 305 d

Res_Fat305 = Annual trend-deviation of average fat content at 305 d

Res_Pro305 = Annual trend-deviation of average protein content at 305 d

Res_Duration = Annual trend-deviation of average lactation duration per cow

Res_CalvInt = Annual trend-deviation of average calving interval of cows

Res_Calv = Annual trend-deviation of number of cows that calve

Res_Long = Annual trend-deviation of average productive longevity of cows

Res_Size = Annual trend-deviation of number of milking cows in herd

MY305_{herd} = average milk yield of cows in herds at 305 days in kg

Prim_{herd} = % of primiparous cows in herd ; Size_{herd} = number of milking cows

Area = geographical area of herd; levels : LI-N = Littoral Normand, NE-L = Nord-Est Loire; LI-A = Littoral Atlantique;

AUV = Auvergne ; Breed_{herd} = main breed of herd (>60% of cows); levels : HO = Holstein; MB = Montbéliarde; NM =

Normande; OB = Other Breeds; MX = Mixed with <60% of main breed ; Season_{herd} = main calving season of herd

(>40% of calvings); levels: SP = spring (April, May, June); SU = summer (July, August, September); FA = fall (October,

November, December); WI = winter (January, February, March); NO_S with <40% of calving on each season.

Figure S5. Correlation between herds performances in the studied dataset : correlation coefficient of Pearson (Kendall, 1973) generated between each herd-year variable in the dataset*.

*MY305: average milk yield of cows in herds at 305 days in kg/cow
 Fat305: average fat content of milk at 305 days in g/kg/cow
 Prot305: average protein content of milk at 305 days in g/kg/cow
 Duration: average herd-level lactation duration in d/cow
 CalvInt: average interval between calvings in d/cow
 Calv: recalving number in herd
 Long: average herd-level productive longevity in days
 Size: number of milking cows

Average milk yield of herd at 305d (MY305) was positively correlated with average lactation duration (Duration_{herd}) and negatively correlated with average productive longevity and number of recalving cows (Long_{herd}, Calv_{herd}). Average milk protein and fat content (Prot305_{herd}, Fat305_{herd}) were strongly and positively correlated to each other, and average productive longevity and primiparous rate (Prim_{herd} and Long_{herd}) were logically strongly negatively correlated.

Figure S6. Visualization of marginal prediction of herd response to annual heat load, on average and depending on 6 herd characteristics, from the linear mixed models selected in the study. Residuals performances (Res_Y) are predicted in raw unit. Three performance deviations were considered: Milk Yield at 305 days in kg/cow (Res_MY305), number of recalving cows (Res_Calv) and number of milking cows in herd (Res_Size).

Legend from top to bottom:

Averaged prediction for an average herd of 48 milking cows, with 35% of primiparous cows. 7,535 kg of milk at 305 days, 1,345 days of average productive longevity, and intermediate values between breed, calving season, and area groups.

Averaged prediction depending on geographical area: *Auvergne* (AUV) in purple, *Littoral-Atlantique* (LI-A) in green, *Littoral-Normand* (LI-N) in brown, *Nord-Est Loire* (NE-L) in yellow.

Averaged prediction depending on main calving season: No_season (spread calvings) in yellow, groups calving in Spring in green, in Summer in orange, in Fall in purple, in Winter in blue.

Averaged prediction depending on two levels of milk production at 305 days (low MY305 herds in purple, 6,500 kg/cow; median MY305 herds in green, 7,500 kg/cow; high MY305 herds in blue, 8,500 kg/cow).

Averaged prediction depending on main breed of herd: Montbéliarde (MB) in purple, Mixed herds (MX) in yellow, Normande (NM) in green, Other Breeds (OB) in orange, Holstein (HO) in blue.

Averaged prediction depending on three levels of herd size (small herds in purple, 30 cows; median herds in green, 45 cows; large herds in blue, 60 cows).

Averaged prediction depending on three levels of the primiparous rate in the herd (low primiparous rate in purple, 30% of primiparous cows; median in green, 35% of primiparous cows; high in blue, 40% of primiparous cows).